

Water-Sediment-Toxicity-Test with *Myriophyllum* sp. (OECD 239-2014): 2024-0001-SAMs

General:

Test identification	2024-0001-SAMs
Test item	PG24-001/1-1
Unit of test item concentration	µg/L
Start of experiment on day	30.1.2024
Date and time of the evaluation	04.03.2024; 18:18:55
Number of shoots per vessel (either in one pot or in individual pots)	3
Raw data filename:	2024-0001-SAMsToxRat 3.3.0 Test.xls

Test design

Number of treatments (incl. control(s))	7
Duration of the test	14 d
Measurement interval	0 d
Measurement variable	Biomass, Length and Growth rates
Test system	<i>Myriophyllum</i> spicatum
Statistical design	Hypothesis testing () and regression (x)

Comments: Fresh weight and dry weight: without roots
shoot length: above sediment
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Find validity information on the next page !

Validity of the Water-Sediment Myriophyllum Test (OECD 239)

Tab. 1: Validity of the Water-Sediment Myriophyllum Test (OECD 239): FW: fresh weight; TSL: total shoot length; CV: coefficient of variation; OECD: required by OECD; User: user settings; Achieved: result of the current test. In FW growth rate and doubling time proved to be 0,190 1/d and 3,6 d, respectively, and in TSL 0,129 1/d and 5,4 d, respectively.

Criterion	OECD	User	Achieved	Valid
FW factor	2,0	2,0	14,3	Yes
TSL factor	2,0	2,0	6,1	Yes
CV% Yield FW	35,0	35,0	3,7	Yes

All validity criteria are fulfilled; thus the test is valid.

Fresh Weight (Pseudoreplicates) (Raw Data)

Summary of Results for all Endpoints at the End of Exposure Period

Tab. 2: Summary of Results for all Endpoints at the End of Exposure Period: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

Critical Conc.s [$\mu\text{g/L}$]

Yield FW			
	EC10		699,040
95%-CL	lower		567,122
	upper		861,642
	EC20		1055,297
95%-CL	lower		719,913
	upper		1522,806
	EC50		n.d.
95%-CL	lower		n.d.
	upper		n.d.
Yield FW	LOEC		400,000
	NOEC		200,000
Growth Rate FW			
	EC10		1222,897
95%-CL	lower		822,424
	upper		1818,375

Tab. 2 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints at the End of Exposure Period: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

	EC20	n.d.
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
	EC50	n.d.
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
Growth Rate FW	LOEC	400,000
	NOEC	200,000
Yield DW		
	EC10	0,000
95%-CL	lower	0,000
	upper	n.d.
	EC20	0,000
95%-CL	lower	0,000
	upper	n.d.
	EC50	n.d.
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
Yield DW	LOEC	n.d.
	NOEC	n.d.
Growth Rate DW		
	EC10	0,000
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.

Tab. 2 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints at the End of Exposure Period: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

	EC20	0,000
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
	EC50	n.d.
95%-CL	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
Growth Rate DW	LOEC	n.d.
	NOEC	n.d.
		0-14 d
Yield TSL		
95%-CL	EC10	26,732
	lower	16,148
	upper	44,253
95%-CL	EC20	57,185
	lower	35,146
	upper	93,206
95%-CL	EC50	244,948
	lower	134,410
	upper	440,533
Yield TSL	LOEC	<=25,000
	NOEC	<25,000
Growth Rate TSL		
95%-CL	EC10	50,112
	lower	27,753
	upper	90,484

Tab. 2 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints at the End of Exposure Period: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

	EC20	116,306
95%-CL	lower	64,527
	upper	210,000
	EC50	582,289
95%-CL	lower	267,173
	upper	1219,528
Growth Rate TSL	LOEC	50,000
	NOEC	25,000

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons or inappropriate data

Fresh Weight (Pseudoreplicates) [mg] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 3: Fresh weight (pseudoreplicates) of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of pseudoreplicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Fresh Weight)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57

Tab. 3 (continued): Fresh weight (pseudoreplicates) of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of pseudoreplicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Fresh Weight)

Mean:	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
Std.Dev.:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
n:	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
CV:	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
14 d	2608,17	2652,36	2620,14	2569,74	2647,79	2551,75	2282,07
	2512,89	2878,01	2699,06	2365,65	2858,47	2548,57	2712,75
	2651,18	2704,34	2692,15	2709,20	2706,59	2465,15	2206,93
	2627,62	2705,09	2663,35	2641,35	2812,29	2765,79	2131,23
	2765,64	2692,27	2908,48	2580,26	2729,71	2905,74	2401,47
	2569,13	2584,72	2755,26	2851,43	2279,49	2686,81	2111,11
	2749,74	2544,56	2621,02	2478,77	2742,48	2666,20	2577,38
	2980,61	2807,10	2531,82	2763,08	2607,05	2474,01	2402,39
	2639,19	2320,19	2366,70	2691,21	2621,84	2414,13	2242,23
	2651,12	2746,27	2638,10	2501,56	2792,70	2446,32	2244,78
	2928,64	2788,23	2929,89	2634,06	2578,44	2746,97	2411,26
	2698,75	2431,29	2521,77	2607,95	2651,67	2579,78	2582,60
	2425,35	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2943,76	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3018,43	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2810,79	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2724,25	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2969,52	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	2737,49	2654,54	2662,31	2616,19	2669,04	2604,27	2358,85
Std.Dev.:	172,957	160,840	157,051	131,584	150,442	151,318	190,286
n:	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
CV:	6,3	6,1	5,9	5,0	5,6	5,8	8,1

Fresh Weight (Raw Data)

Fresh Weight [mg] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 4: Fresh weight of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Fresh Weight)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57

Mean:	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57	191,57
Std.Dev.:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
n:	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
CV:	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

14 d	2590,75	2744,90	2670,45	2548,20	2737,62	2521,82	2400,58
	2654,13	2660,69	2775,70	2691,01	2607,16	2786,11	2214,60
	2789,85	2557,28	2506,51	2644,35	2657,12	2518,11	2407,33
	2759,50	2655,26	2696,59	2581,19	2674,27	2591,02	2412,88
	2795,85	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2834,85	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mean:	2737,49	2654,54	2662,31	2616,19	2669,04	2604,27	2358,85
Std.Dev.:	94,439	76,731	113,093	63,874	53,854	125,781	96,296
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	3,4	2,9	4,2	2,4	2,0	4,8	4,1

Yield FW (Data)

Yield FW [mg] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 5: Yield FW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Fresh Weight)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Mean:	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Std.Dev.:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
n:	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
CV:							

Tab. 5 (continued): Yield FW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Fresh Weight)

14 d	2399,18	2553,33	2478,88	2356,63	2546,05	2330,25	2209,01
	2462,56	2469,12	2584,13	2499,44	2415,59	2594,54	2023,03
	2598,28	2365,71	2314,94	2452,78	2465,55	2326,54	2215,76
	2567,93	2463,69	2505,02	2389,62	2482,70	2399,45	2221,31
	2604,28	-	-	-	-	-	-
	2643,28	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	2545,92	2462,97	2470,74	2424,62	2477,47	2412,70	2167,28
Std.Dev.:	94,439	76,731	113,093	63,874	53,854	125,781	96,296
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	3,7	3,1	4,6	2,6	2,2	5,2	4,4

Fig. 1: Yield FW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (EC_x) for Yield FW at 14 d

Yield FW [mg] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 14 d.

Tab. 6: %Reduction of yield FW caused by the test item after 14 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	2545,92	94,439	6	
25,000	2462,97	76,731	4	3,3
50,000	2470,74	113,093	4	3,0
100,000	2424,62	63,874	4	4,8
200,000	2477,47	53,854	4	2,7
400,000	2412,70	125,781	4	5,2

800,000 2167,28 96,296 4 14,9

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

The optimization converged thus fitting was successful (Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)).

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 7: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with yield FW at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b0	2485,202	21,406	2441,281	2529,123	116,099	<0.001
b1	2,845	0,044	2,754	2,935	64,260	<0.001
b2	0,407	0,163	0,073	0,741	2,498	0,009

Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,589; adjusted R^2 : 0,558. Residual standard error: 93,50352. Akaike Criterion (AIC): 308,719. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,958$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 8: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with yield FW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$: probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	338520,74	2	169260,37	19,360	<0.001
Residuals	236058,53	27	8742,91		
- Lack of Fit	39209,87	4	9802,47	1,145	0,360
- Pure Error	196848,66	23	8558,64		
Total	574822,21	29			

Since $p(F|Regression) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model. Since $p(F|Lack of Fit) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit.

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 9: Observed values in yield FW after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	2399,176	2545,917	2485,202
0,001	2462,559	2545,917	2485,202
0,001	2598,276	2545,917	2485,202
0,001	2567,933	2545,917	2485,202
0,001	2604,276	2545,917	2485,202
0,001	2643,283	2545,917	2485,202
25,000	2553,333	2462,965	2485,201
25,000	2469,123	2462,965	2485,201
25,000	2365,713	2462,965	2485,201
25,000	2463,693	2462,965	2485,201
50,000	2478,879	2470,741	2485,151
50,000	2584,126	2470,741	2485,151
50,000	2314,943	2470,741	2485,151
50,000	2505,016	2470,741	2485,151

100,000	2356,626	2424,618	2484,229
100,000	2499,443	2424,618	2484,229
100,000	2452,783	2424,618	2484,229
100,000	2389,620	2424,618	2484,229
200,000	2546,046	2477,473	2474,218
200,000	2415,593	2477,473	2474,218
200,000	2465,553	2477,473	2474,218
200,000	2482,699	2477,473	2474,218
400,000	2330,253	2412,698	2410,143
400,000	2594,543	2412,698	2410,143
400,000	2326,543	2412,698	2410,143
400,000	2399,453	2412,698	2410,143
800,000	2209,013	2167,279	2167,907
800,000	2023,033	2167,279	2167,907
800,000	2215,763	2167,279	2167,907
800,000	2221,310	2167,279	2167,907

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 10: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with yield FW at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	699,040	1055,297	n.d.
lower 95%-cl	567,122	719,913	n.d.
upper 95%-cl	861,642	1522,806	n.d.

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 2: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on yield FW of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Threshold concentrations (NOEC) for Yield FW at 14 d

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 11: Statistical characteristics with yield FW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	2545,92	94,439	6	94,439	6	94,439	3,7	38,555	1,5	2446,81	2645,02
25,000	2462,97	76,731	4	76,731	4	76,731	3,1	38,365	1,6	2340,87	2585,06
50,000	2470,74	113,093	4	113,093	4	113,093	4,6	56,547	2,3	2290,78	2650,70
100,000	2424,62	63,874	4	63,874	4	63,874	2,6	31,937	1,3	2322,98	2526,26
200,000	2477,47	53,854	4	53,854	4	53,854	2,2	26,927	1,1	2391,78	2563,17
400,000	2412,70	125,781	4	125,781	4	125,781	5,2	62,891	2,6	2212,55	2612,84
800,000	2167,28	96,296	4	96,296	4	96,296	4,4	48,148	2,2	2014,05	2320,51

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 12: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with yield FW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(H_0) is accepted.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	n
NK	2545,92	94,439	6
25,000	2462,97	76,731	4
50,000	2470,74	113,093	4
100,000	2424,62	63,874	4
200,000	2477,47	53,854	4
400,000	2412,70	125,781	4
800,000	2167,28	96,296	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 30; Shapiro-Wilk's W = 0,972; p(W) = 0,598; p(W) is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 13: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with yield FW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	9321,8916	6	1553,6486	0,617	0,714
Residuals	57892,4379	23	2517,0625		
Total	67214,330	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.

A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 14: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with yield FW at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (Ho: Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	1229,7166	231,2823	23	5,317	<0.001
Quadratic	977,1294	402,3691	23	2,428	0,012

The linear trend is significant (p <= 0,05) The quadratic trend is significant (p <= 0,05)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 15: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with yield FW at 14 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for Ho: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; df = N - k; N: sum of treatment replicates n(i); k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	2545,92	92,5129						
25,000	2462,97	92,5129	23	2466,85	-4,0	-1,32	-1,71	-
50,000	2470,74	92,5129	23	2466,85	-4,2	-1,32	-1,78	-
100,000	2424,62	92,5129	23	2451,05	-4,2	-1,59	-1,81	-
200,000	2477,47	92,5129	23	2451,05	-4,3	-1,59	-1,82	-
400,000	2412,70	92,5129	23	2412,70	-4,3	-2,23	-1,83	+
800,000	2167,28	92,5129	23	2167,28	-4,3	-6,34	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

A NOEC of 200,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ is suggested by the program.

Growth Rate FW (Data)

Growth Rate FW [1/d] of Myriophyllum spicatum as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 16: Growthrate FW of Myriophyllum spicatum as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (calculated from RawData Fresh Weight)

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000

Tab. 16 (continued): Growth rate FW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (calculated from RawData Fresh Weight)

Mean:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Std.Dev.:	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
n:	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
CV:							
14 d	0,186	0,190	0,188	0,185	0,190	0,184	0,181
	0,188	0,188	0,191	0,189	0,186	0,191	0,175
	0,191	0,185	0,184	0,187	0,188	0,184	0,181
	0,191	0,188	0,189	0,186	0,188	0,186	0,181
	0,191	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,192	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	0,190	0,188	0,188	0,187	0,188	0,186	0,179
Std.Dev.:	0,0025	0,0021	0,0031	0,0017	0,0014	0,0034	0,0030
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	1,3	1,1	1,6	0,9	0,8	1,8	1,7

Fig. 3: Growth rate FW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Growth Rate FW at 14 d

Growth Rate FW [1/d] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 14 d.

25,000	0,188	0,0021	4	1,2
50,000	0,188	0,0031	4	1,1
100,000	0,187	0,0017	4	1,7
200,000	0,188	0,0014	4	0,9
400,000	0,186	0,0034	4	1,9
800,000	0,179	0,0030	4	5,6

PLEASE NOTE: The non-linear regression procedure was terminated without achieving convergence due to mathematical problems (Stop Reason = C Norm(Grad) < gradient tolerance (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)). Please check whether the fit is nonetheless acceptable or try whether other options/functions lead to convergence.

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 18: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate FW at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	0,188	0,001	0,187	0,190	319,928	<0.001
b_1	3,087	0,084	2,915	3,260	36,767	<0.001
b_2	0,481	0,193	0,084	0,878	2,485	0,010

Not converged due to mathematical problems (

R^2 : 0,609; adjusted R^2 : 0,580. Residual standard error: 0,00255. Akaike Criterion (AIC): -321,792. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,810$..

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 19: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate FW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$: probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	0,000	2	0,000	21,004	<0.001
Residuals	0,000	27	0,000		
- Lack of Fit	0,000	4	0,000	1,063	0,397
- Pure Error	0,000	23	0,000		
Total	0,000	29			

Since $p(F|\text{Regression}) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model.. Since $p(F|\text{Lack of Fit}) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 20: Observed values in growth rate FW after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	0,186	0,1899	0,1883
0,001	0,188	0,1899	0,1883
0,001	0,191	0,1899	0,1883
0,001	0,191	0,1899	0,1883
0,001	0,191	0,1899	0,1883
0,001	0,192	0,1899	0,1883

25,000	0,190	0,1877	0,1883
25,000	0,188	0,1877	0,1883
25,000	0,185	0,1877	0,1883
25,000	0,188	0,1877	0,1883
50,000	0,188	0,1879	0,1883
50,000	0,191	0,1879	0,1883
50,000	0,184	0,1879	0,1883
50,000	0,189	0,1879	0,1883
100,000	0,185	0,1867	0,1883
100,000	0,189	0,1867	0,1883
100,000	0,187	0,1867	0,1883
100,000	0,186	0,1867	0,1883
200,000	0,190	0,1881	0,1880
200,000	0,186	0,1881	0,1880
200,000	0,188	0,1881	0,1880
200,000	0,188	0,1881	0,1880
400,000	0,184	0,1863	0,1863
400,000	0,191	0,1863	0,1863
400,000	0,184	0,1863	0,1863
400,000	0,186	0,1863	0,1863
800,000	0,181	0,1793	0,1793
800,000	0,175	0,1793	0,1793
800,000	0,181	0,1793	0,1793
800,000	0,181	0,1793	0,1793

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 21: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate FW at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [µg/L]	1222,896	n.d.	n.d.
lower 95%-cl	822,424	n.d.	n.d.
upper 95%-cl	1818,375	n.d.	n.d.

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 4: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on growthrate FW of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 22: Statistical characteristics with growth rate FW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	0,190	0,191	0,186	0,192	6	0,0025	1,3	0,0010	0,5	0,187	0,193
25,000	0,188	0,188	0,185	0,190	4	0,0021	1,1	0,0010	0,6	0,184	0,191
50,000	0,188	0,189	0,184	0,191	4	0,0031	1,6	0,0015	0,8	0,183	0,193
100,000	0,187	0,187	0,185	0,189	4	0,0017	0,9	0,0009	0,5	0,184	0,189
200,000	0,188	0,188	0,186	0,190	4	0,0014	0,8	0,0007	0,4	0,186	0,190
400,000	0,186	0,185	0,184	0,191	4	0,0034	1,8	0,0017	0,9	0,181	0,192
800,000	0,179	0,181	0,175	0,181	4	0,0030	1,7	0,0015	0,8	0,175	0,184

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 23: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with growth rate FW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are dues to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(Ho) is accepted.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	s	n
NK	0,190	0,0025	6
25,000	0,188	0,0021	4
50,000	0,188	0,0031	4
100,000	0,187	0,0017	4
200,000	0,188	0,0014	4
400,000	0,186	0,0034	4
800,000	0,179	0,0030	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 24; Shapiro-Wilk's W = 0,968; p(W) = 0,630; p(W) is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed (p > 0,01).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 24: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with growth rate FW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	0,00001	6	0,00000	0,647	0,692
Residuals	0,00004	23	0,00000		
Total	0,0001	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 25: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with growth rate FW at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	0,03452	0,00635	23	5,434	<0.001
Quadratic	0,02899	0,01105	23	2,623	0,008

The linear trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$) The quadratic trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 26: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with growth rate FW at 14 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates $n(i)$; k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	0,190	0,00254						
25,000	0,188	0,00254	23	0,188	-1,5	-1,28	-1,71	-
50,000	0,188	0,00254	23	0,188	-1,5	-1,28	-1,78	-
100,000	0,187	0,00254	23	0,187	-1,6	-1,52	-1,81	-
200,000	0,188	0,00254	23	0,187	-1,6	-1,52	-1,82	-
400,000	0,186	0,00254	23	0,186	-1,6	-2,19	-1,83	+
800,000	0,179	0,00254	23	0,179	-1,6	-6,49	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

A NOEC of 200,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ is suggested by the program.

Yield DW (Data)

Yield DW [mg] of Myriophyllum spicatum as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 27: Yield DW of Myriophyllum spicatum as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Dry

Weight)								
Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000	
0 d	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
Mean:	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	
Std.Dev.:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	
n:	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
CV:								
14 d	45,11	48,94	44,71	45,86	54,72	40,66	44,60	
	47,61	38,48	49,10	46,64	52,47	54,43	45,10	
	56,04	40,26	39,53	44,43	49,52	41,59	48,72	
	51,42	41,43	48,72	37,79	46,20	52,01	39,76	
	51,77	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	71,50	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Mean:	53,91	42,28	45,52	43,68	50,73	47,17	44,55	
Std.Dev.:	9,400	4,604	4,454	4,034	3,695	7,061	3,678	
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4	
CV:	17,4	10,9	9,8	9,2	7,3	15,0	8,3	

Fig. 5: Yield DW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Yield DW at 14 d

Yield DW [mg] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 14 d.

Tab. 28: %Reduction of yield DW caused by the test item after 14 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	53,91	9,400	6	
25,000	42,28	4,604	4	21,6
50,000	45,52	4,454	4	15,6
100,000	43,68	4,034	4	19,0
200,000	50,73	3,695	4	5,9
400,000	47,17	7,061	4	12,5
800,000	44,55	3,678	4	17,4

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 29: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with yield DW at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	85,083	46,859	-11,064	181,231	1,816	0,040
b_1	-25,119	19,645	-65,427	15,188	-1,279	0,106
b_2	23,029	7,816	6,991	39,067	2,946	0,003

Stop Reason = Iterations > Max. Iterations (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,205; adjusted R^2 : 0,147. Residual standard error: 6,32884. Akaike Criterion (AIC): 147,146. ShapiroWilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,099$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 30: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with yield DW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$: probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	277,44	2	138,72	3,463	0,046
Residuals	1081,46	27	40,05		
- Lack of Fit	236,63	4	59,16	1,611	0,205
- Pure Error	844,84	23	36,73		
Total	1350,17	29			

Since $p(F|\text{Regression}) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model.. Since $p(F|\text{Lack of Fit}) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 31: Observed values in yield DW after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	45,106	53,907	53,255
0,001	47,609	53,907	53,255
0,001	56,039	53,907	53,255
0,001	51,416	53,907	53,255
0,001	51,773	53,907	53,255
0,001	71,496	53,907	53,255

25,000	48,939	42,277	46,945
25,000	38,483	42,277	46,945
25,000	40,259	42,277	46,945
25,000	41,426	42,277	46,945
50,000	44,713	45,515	46,504
50,000	49,099	45,515	46,504
50,000	39,533	45,515	46,504
50,000	48,716	45,515	46,504
100,000	45,863	43,680	46,063
100,000	46,639	43,680	46,063
100,000	44,433	43,680	46,063
100,000	37,786	43,680	46,063
200,000	54,723	50,727	45,622
200,000	52,466	50,727	45,622
200,000	49,523	50,727	45,622
200,000	46,196	50,727	45,622
400,000	40,663	47,173	45,180
400,000	54,426	47,173	45,180
400,000	41,593	47,173	45,180
400,000	52,013	47,173	45,180
800,000	44,603	44,546	44,737
800,000	45,103	44,546	44,737
800,000	48,716	44,546	44,737
800,000	39,763	44,546	44,737

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 32: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with yield DW at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	0,000	0,000	n.d.
lower 95%-cl	0,000	0,000	n.d.
upper 95%-cl	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b_1 ; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 6: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on yield DW of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 33: Statistical characteristics with yield DW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	53,91	51,59	45,11	71,50	6	9,400	17,4	3,838	7,1	44,04	63,77
25,000	42,28	40,84	38,48	48,94	4	4,604	10,9	2,302	5,4	34,95	49,60
50,000	45,52	46,71	39,53	49,10	4	4,454	9,8	2,227	4,9	38,43	52,60
100,000	43,68	45,15	37,79	46,64	4	4,034	9,2	2,017	4,6	37,26	50,10
200,000	50,73	50,99	46,20	54,72	4	3,695	7,3	1,848	3,6	44,85	56,61
400,000	47,17	46,80	40,66	54,43	4	7,061	15,0	3,530	7,5	35,94	58,41
800,000	44,55	44,85	39,76	48,72	4	3,678	8,3	1,839	4,1	38,69	50,40

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 34: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with yield DW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(Ho) is accepted.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	s	n
NK	53,91	9,400	6
25,000	42,28	4,604	4
50,000	45,52	4,454	4
100,000	43,68	4,034	4
200,000	50,73	3,695	4
400,000	47,17	7,061	4
800,000	44,55	3,678	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 30; Shapiro-Wilk's W = 0,932; p(W) = 0,057; p(W) is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed (p > 0,01).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 35: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with yield DW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	79,3001	6	13,2167	1,176	0,353
Residuals	258,3799	23	11,2339		
Total	337,680	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 36: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with yield DW at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	13,0767	15,1517	23	0,863	0,199
Quadratic	-28,8161	26,3599	23	-1,093	0,143

The linear trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$) The quadratic trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts did not reveal a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was replaced by Dunnett test.

Dunnett's Multiple t-test Procedure

Tab. 37: Dunnett's multiple t-test procedure with yield DW at 14 d: Comparison of treatments with "NK". Significance was $\alpha = 0,050$, one-sided smaller (multiple level); Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates $n(i)$; k: number of treatments).

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	53,91	6,0607					
25,000	42,28	6,0607	23	-17,7	-2,97	-2,43	+
50,000	45,52	6,0607	23	-17,7	-2,14	-2,43	-
100,000	43,68	6,0607	23	-17,7	-2,61	-2,43	+
200,000	50,73	6,0607	23	-17,7	-0,81	-2,43	-
400,000	47,17	6,0607	23	-17,7	-1,72	-2,43	-
800,000	44,55	6,0607	23	-17,7	-2,39	-2,43	-

+: significant; -: non-significant

The NOEC cannot be determined by the program (expert judgement required).

Growth Rate DW (Data)

Growth Rate DW [1/d] of Myriophyllum spicatum as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 38: Growth rate DW of Myriophyllum spicatum as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (calculated)

from RawData Dry Weight)

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Mean:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Std.Dev.:	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
n:	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
CV:							
14 d	0,072	0,076	0,072	0,073	0,081	0,068	0,072
	0,075	0,065	0,076	0,074	0,079	0,081	0,072
	0,082	0,067	0,066	0,072	0,077	0,069	0,076
	0,078	0,068	0,076	0,064	0,073	0,079	0,067
	0,079	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,095	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	0,080	0,069	0,072	0,071	0,078	0,074	0,072
Std.Dev.:	0,0080	0,0047	0,0045	0,0043	0,0035	0,0069	0,0038
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	10,0	6,8	6,3	6,0	4,5	9,3	5,3

Fig. 7: Growth rate DW of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Growth Rate DW at 14 d

Growth Rate DW [1/d] in Myriophyllum spicatum after 14 d.

Tab. 39: %Reduction of growth rate DW caused by the test item after 14 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	0,080	0,0080	6	
25,000	0,069	0,0047	4	13,7
50,000	0,072	0,0045	4	9,6
100,000	0,071	0,0043	4	11,9
200,000	0,078	0,0035	4	3,2
400,000	0,074	0,0069	4	7,7
800,000	0,072	0,0038	4	10,7

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 40: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate DW at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	0,121	0,044	0,031	0,211	2,766	0,005
b_1	-33,750	20,628	-76,076	8,576	-1,636	0,057
b_2	35,078	11,187	12,124	58,032	3,136	0,002

Stop Reason = Iterations > Max. Iterations (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,193; adjusted R^2 : 0,133. Residual standard error: 0,00593. Akaike Criterion (AIC): -271,219. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,230$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 41: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate DW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$: probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	0,000	2	0,000	3,222	0,056
Residuals	0,001	27	0,000		
- Lack of Fit	0,000	4	0,000	1,796	0,164
- Pure Error	0,001	23	0,000		
Total	0,001	29			

Since $p(F|_{\text{Regression}}) > 0.05$, the amount of variance explained by the regression model is NOT significant.. Therefore, confidence limits cannot be provided.. Since $p(F|_{\text{Lack of Fit}}) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 42: Observed values in growth rate DW after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	0,072	0,0802	0,0795
0,001	0,075	0,0802	0,0795
0,001	0,082	0,0802	0,0795
0,001	0,078	0,0802	0,0795
0,001	0,079	0,0802	0,0795
0,001	0,095	0,0802	0,0795

25,000	0,076	0,0692	0,0738
25,000	0,065	0,0692	0,0738
25,000	0,067	0,0692	0,0738
25,000	0,068	0,0692	0,0738
50,000	0,072	0,0725	0,0734
50,000	0,076	0,0725	0,0734
50,000	0,066	0,0725	0,0734
50,000	0,076	0,0725	0,0734
100,000	0,073	0,0706	0,0730
100,000	0,074	0,0706	0,0730
100,000	0,072	0,0706	0,0730
100,000	0,064	0,0706	0,0730
200,000	0,081	0,0776	0,0726
200,000	0,079	0,0776	0,0726
200,000	0,077	0,0776	0,0726
200,000	0,073	0,0776	0,0726
400,000	0,068	0,0740	0,0722
400,000	0,081	0,0740	0,0722
400,000	0,069	0,0740	0,0722
400,000	0,079	0,0740	0,0722
800,000	0,072	0,0716	0,0718
800,000	0,072	0,0716	0,0718
800,000	0,076	0,0716	0,0718
800,000	0,067	0,0716	0,0718

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 43: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate DW at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	0,000	0,000	n.d.
lower 95%-cl	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
upper 95%-cl	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

Since a significant lack of fit was found, it is recommended to try other dose/response functions..

Fig. 8: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on growthrate DW of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 44: Statistical characteristics with growth rate DW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	0,080	0,078	0,072	0,095	6	0,0080	10,0	0,0033	4,1	0,072	0,089
25,000	0,069	0,068	0,065	0,076	4	0,0047	6,8	0,0024	3,4	0,062	0,077
50,000	0,072	0,074	0,066	0,076	4	0,0045	6,3	0,0023	3,1	0,065	0,080
100,000	0,071	0,072	0,064	0,074	4	0,0043	6,0	0,0021	3,0	0,064	0,077
200,000	0,078	0,078	0,073	0,081	4	0,0035	4,5	0,0017	2,2	0,072	0,083
400,000	0,074	0,074	0,068	0,081	4	0,0069	9,3	0,0035	4,7	0,063	0,085
800,000	0,072	0,072	0,067	0,076	4	0,0038	5,3	0,0019	2,6	0,066	0,078

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 45: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with growth rate DW at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are dues to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(Ho) is accepted.

Treatm. [µg/L]	Mean	s	n
NK	0,080	0,0080	6
25,000	0,069	0,0047	4
50,000	0,072	0,0045	4
100,000	0,071	0,0043	4
200,000	0,078	0,0035	4
400,000	0,074	0,0069	4
800,000	0,072	0,0038	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 25; Shapiro-Wilk's W = 0,960; p(W) = 0,414; p(W) is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 46: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with growth rate DW at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	0,00005	6	0,00001	0,976	0,464
Residuals	0,00021	23	0,00001		
Total	0,0003	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 47: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with growth rate DW at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	0,01109	0,01402	23	0,791	0,219
Quadratic	-0,02576	0,02439	23	-1,056	0,151

The linear trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$) The quadratic trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts did not reveal a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was replaced by Dunnett test.

Dunnett's Multiple t-test Procedure

Tab. 48: Dunnett's multiple t-test procedure with growth rate DW at 14 d: Comparison of treatments with "NK".

Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller (multiple level); Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for H_0 : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates n(i); k: number of treatments).

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	0,080	0,00561					
25,000	0,069	0,00561	23	-11,0	-3,04	-2,43	+
50,000	0,072	0,00561	23	-11,0	-2,12	-2,43	-
100,000	0,071	0,00561	23	-11,0	-2,63	-2,43	+
200,000	0,078	0,00561	23	-11,0	-0,71	-2,43	-
400,000	0,074	0,00561	23	-11,0	-1,70	-2,43	-
800,000	0,072	0,00561	23	-11,0	-2,38	-2,43	-

+: significant; -: non-significant

The NOEC cannot be determined by the program (expert judgement required).

Lateral Branches Number (Pseudoreplicates) (Raw Data)

Lateral Branches Number (Pseudoreplicates) of Myriophyllum spicatum as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 49: Lateral branches number (pseudoreplicates) of Myriophyllum spicatum as dependent on concentration of the

test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of pseudoreplicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Lateral Branches)

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	6,0	5,0	5,0	4,0	5,0	6,0	5,0
	4,0	4,0	4,0	3,0	7,0	4,0	4,0
	3,0	5,0	2,0	4,0	5,0	6,0	3,0
	3,0	5,0	3,0	5,0	3,0	7,0	3,0
	4,0	4,0	3,0	3,0	4,0	6,0	7,0
	2,0	2,0	6,0	4,0	5,0	3,0	5,0
	4,0	4,0	4,0	2,0	2,0	2,0	4,0
	2,0	5,0	3,0	5,0	4,0	6,0	4,0
	4,0	3,0	3,0	5,0	3,0	3,0	3,0
	3,0	5,0	7,0	6,0	4,0	3,0	4,0
	4,0	3,0	5,0	3,0	3,0	7,0	8,0
	4,0	6,0	5,0	3,0	2,0	6,0	7,0
	3,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	3,9	4,3	4,2	3,9	3,9	4,9	4,8
Std.Dev.:	1,16	1,14	1,47	1,16	1,44	1,78	1,71
n:	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
CV:	29,5	26,8	35,2	29,7	36,9	36,2	36,0
7 d	4,0	4,0	5,0	7,0	6,0	7,0	6,0
	4,0	7,0	6,0	7,0	5,0	5,0	7,0
	3,0	8,0	5,0	6,0	8,0	5,0	4,0
	3,0	6,0	8,0	7,0	7,0	10,0	4,0
	6,0	6,0	5,0	4,0	6,0	7,0	7,0
	3,0	4,0	7,0	8,0	5,0	8,0	5,0
	5,0	6,0	6,0	6,0	9,0	7,0	4,0
	6,0	9,0	6,0	6,0	7,0	7,0	6,0
	5,0	5,0	5,0	4,0	7,0	5,0	5,0
	5,0	6,0	9,0	8,0	4,0	9,0	8,0
	7,0	5,0	6,0	6,0	4,0	6,0	8,0
	9,0	8,0	6,0	5,0	5,0	8,0	8,0
	3,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mean:	5,0	6,2	6,2	6,2	6,1	7,0	6,0
Std.Dev.:	1,57	1,59	1,27	1,34	1,56	1,60	1,60
n:	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
CV:	31,4	25,7	20,6	21,7	25,7	22,8	26,6
14 d	4,0	3,0	3,0	6,0	5,0	7,0	6,0
	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	6,0	6,0	6,0
	4,0	4,0	3,0	5,0	7,0	8,0	4,0
	5,0	6,0	5,0	6,0	9,0	10,0	8,0
	6,0	6,0	8,0	4,0	8,0	8,0	8,0
	3,0	4,0	5,0	7,0	5,0	5,0	5,0
	3,0	5,0	3,0	4,0	9,0	7,0	9,0
	6,0	6,0	4,0	4,0	6,0	6,0	6,0
	5,0	4,0	4,0	6,0	8,0	6,0	6,0
	3,0	6,0	8,0	5,0	7,0	7,0	5,0
	5,0	5,0	7,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	7,0
	5,0	5,0	3,0	5,0	7,0	7,0	5,0
	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	7,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	3,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
	6,0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	4,6	4,9	4,8	5,2	6,8	6,8	6,3
Std.Dev.:	1,25	1,00	1,90	0,94	1,47	1,40	1,48
n:	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
CV:	27,4	20,3	39,3	18,1	21,5	20,5	23,8

Total LB Length (Pseudoreplicates) (Raw Data)

Total LB Length (Pseudoreplicates) [cm] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 50: Total LB length (pseudoreplicates) of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of pseudoreplicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Length Lat Branches)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25	50	100	200	400	800
0 d	2,0	1,9	1,5	1,2	2,1	2,1	1,4
	1,9	1,2	1,2	1,2	2,0	1,3	1,2
	0,9	0,8	0,6	1,3	2,4	1,7	0,6
	1,1	1,5	2,4	1,8	1,9	1,5	1,1
	1,2	1,3	1,3	1,0	1,0	1,4	1,6
	0,4	0,4	1,9	1,3	1,3	0,8	1,3
	1,7	1,0	1,5	0,5	0,4	0,7	1,8
	0,5	1,6	0,7	1,3	1,3	1,2	1,1
	1,5	0,5	1,4	1,4	0,6	0,8	0,6

	1,1	2,2	1,8	1,4	1,3	0,8	1,2
	1,4	0,8	1,9	0,8	1,0	2,6	1,7
	1,5	3,0	1,0	1,2	0,7	1,5	1,4
	0,8						
	1,3						
	1,2						
	1,3						
	2,9						
	1,5						
Replicates	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
Mean	1,3	1,4	1,4	1,2	1,3	1,4	1,3
Std.Dev	0,58	0,75	0,52	0,32	0,64	0,58	0,38
CV%	42,8	55,7	36,5	27,1	48,1	42,1	30,2
7 d	11,5	10,5	6,6	7,8	7,8	5,8	4,7
	11,5	8,9	9,1	7,3	7,0	5,5	5,4
	10,0	7,5	6,4	9,7	8,8	6,6	1,8
	9,0	9,5	17,7	11,0	8,4	9,4	5,5
	14,0	9,6	6,5	5,3	6,5	7,8	8,3
	8,0	6,0	11,5	9,1	6,6	5,1	6,0
	13,1	9,2	6,2	4,7	5,1	5,8	4,1
	5,7	13,1	5,0	8,2	5,8	6,9	5,2
	11,0	6,5	9,0	5,6	4,4	4,6	3,5
	9,0	12,7	15,8	9,2	7,3	5,9	10,0
	13,0	8,1	6,3	7,1	5,2	5,2	4,6
	18,1	14,0	8,2	7,7	4,7	7,0	6,9
	7,5						
	13,7						
	8,5						
	9,0						
	16,5						
	7,2						

Tab. 50 (continued): Total LB length (pseudoreplicates) of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of pseudoreplicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Length Lat Branches)

Replicates	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
Mean	10,9	9,6	9,0	7,7	6,5	6,3	5,5
Std.Dev	3,33	2,56	4,03	1,88	1,45	1,34	2,16
CV%	30,6	26,5	44,7	24,4	22,5	21,2	39,3
14 d	25,4	16,4	15,3	20,2	15,2	9,5	9,3
	29,8	21,5	21,0	17,5	15,4	8,8	9,8
	24,0	23,1	15,4	23,7	16,6	11,6	2,5
	28,0	26,0	25,1	20,7	16,1	13,4	8,5
	33,7	21,8	42,8	11,6	11,1	14,6	8,6
	17,9	20,6	21,0	26,1	10,8	9,6	5,4
	27,3	20,4	19,1	11,4	12,3	10,2	13,2
	33,6	26,4	13,9	17,5	17,2	8,0	8,1
	20,4	20,0	22,6	20,2	11,7	7,2	4,7
	19,2	24,4	20,8	17,4	12,8	7,4	6,8
	27,8	27,8	34,0	13,5	11,4	9,4	6,9
	26,7	18,5	14,1	17,0	11,5	14,0	6,2
	20,5						
	25,7						
	38,3						
	17,6						
	16,5						
	28,1						
Replicates	18	12	12	12	12	12	12
Mean	25,6	22,2	22,1	18,1	13,5	10,3	7,5
Std.Dev	6,10	3,41	8,61	4,49	2,40	2,54	2,75
CV%	23,8	15,3	39,0	24,8	17,7	24,6	36,7

Total Shoot Length (Raw Data)

Total Shoot Length [cm] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 51: Total shoot length of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Tot Shoot Length)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	6,93	7,60	7,27	7,73	9,17	7,53	8,23
	6,70	6,70	8,20	7,37	8,40	7,23	8,17
	6,90	6,87	6,87	7,73	6,43	6,40	7,50
	7,33	8,00	9,40	7,13	7,00	8,30	8,77
	6,77	-	-	-	-	-	-
	9,07	-	-	-	-	-	-

Mean:	7,28	7,29	7,93	7,49	7,75	7,37	8,17
Std.Dev.:	0,901	0,613	1,126	0,295	1,255	0,786	0,519
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	12,4	8,4	14,2	3,9	16,2	10,7	6,4
7 d	25,00	22,97	20,87	19,77	17,87	13,30	12,63
	24,33	20,70	23,07	18,80	18,17	16,60	14,77
	23,43	21,77	18,57	18,00	14,43	14,27	13,10
	27,87	23,27	25,93	18,33	15,23	14,70	16,00
	24,07	-	-	-	-	-	-
	25,90	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	25,10	22,18	22,11	18,73	16,43	14,72	14,12
Std.Dev.:	1,596	1,178	3,143	0,768	1,871	1,385	1,550
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	6,4	5,3	14,2	4,1	11,4	9,4	11,0
14 d	44,60	39,63	36,33	34,97	29,53	19,93	16,97
	43,80	39,20	43,83	34,40	27,63	25,53	16,93
	46,37	38,47	35,53	34,40	28,03	19,73	18,87
	43,73	39,43	43,07	29,67	24,97	21,13	16,73
	47,37	-	-	-	-	-	-
	40,63	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	44,42	39,18	39,69	33,36	27,54	21,58	17,38
Std.Dev.:	2,354	0,510	4,363	2,476	1,902	2,705	1,000
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	5,3	1,3	11,0	7,4	6,9	12,5	5,8

Yield TSL (Data)

Yield TSL [cm] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 52: Yield TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Tot Shoot Length)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
	0,00	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,00	-	-	-	-	-	-

Tab. 52 (continued): Yield TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (from RawData Tot Shoot Length)

Mean:	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
Std.Dev.:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:							
7 d	18,07	15,37	13,60	12,03	8,70	5,77	4,40
	17,63	14,00	14,87	11,43	9,77	9,37	6,60
	16,53	14,90	11,70	10,27	8,00	7,87	5,60
	20,53	15,27	16,53	11,20	8,23	6,40	7,23
	17,30	-	-	-	-	-	-
	16,83	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	17,82	14,88	14,17	11,23	8,67	7,35	5,96
Std.Dev.:	1,439	0,622	2,041	0,734	0,784	1,607	1,237
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	8,1	4,2	14,4	6,5	9,0	21,9	20,8
14 d	37,67	32,03	29,07	27,23	20,37	12,40	8,73
	37,10	32,50	35,63	27,03	19,23	18,30	8,77
	39,47	31,60	28,67	26,67	21,60	13,33	11,37
	36,40	31,43	33,67	22,53	17,97	12,83	7,97
	40,60	-	-	-	-	-	-
	31,57	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	37,13	31,89	31,76	25,87	19,79	14,22	9,21
Std.Dev.:	3,139	0,478	3,438	2,235	1,554	2,749	1,486
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	8,5	1,5	10,8	8,6	7,9	19,3	16,1

Fig. 9: Yield TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Yield TSL at 7 d

Yield TSL [cm] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 7 d.

Tab. 53: %Reduction of yield TSL caused by the test item after 7 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	17,82	1,439	6	
25,000	14,88	0,622	4	16,5
50,000	14,17	2,041	4	20,4
100,000	11,23	0,734	4	37,0
200,000	8,67	0,784	4	51,3
400,000	7,35	1,607	4	58,7
800,000	5,96	1,237	4	66,6

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

The optimization converged thus fitting was successful (Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)).

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 54: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 7 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	17,893	0,530	16,805	18,980	33,756	<0.001
b_1	1,077	0,154	0,761	1,393	7,002	<0.001
b_2	1,014	0,105	0,798	1,230	9,642	<0.001

Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,933; adjusted R^2 : 0,928. Residual standard error: 1,31299. Akaike Criterion (AIC): 52,777. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,057$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 55: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 7 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$:

probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	535,06	2	267,53	155,186	<0.001
Residuals	46,55	27	1,72		
- Lack of Fit	6,74	4	1,68	0,973	0,442
- Pure Error	39,81	23	1,73		
Total	573,53	29			

Since $p(F|Regression) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model.. Since $p(F|Lack of Fit) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 56: Observed values in yield TSL after 7 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	18,067	17,817	17,893
0,001	17,633	17,817	17,893
0,001	16,533	17,817	17,893
0,001	20,533	17,817	17,893
0,001	17,300	17,817	17,893
0,001	16,833	17,817	17,893
25,000	15,367	14,883	14,900
25,000	14,000	14,883	14,900
25,000	14,900	14,883	14,900
25,000	15,267	14,883	14,900
50,000	13,600	14,175	13,384
50,000	14,867	14,175	13,384
50,000	11,700	14,175	13,384
50,000	16,533	14,175	13,384
100,000	12,033	11,233	11,538
100,000	11,433	11,233	11,538
100,000	10,267	11,233	11,538
100,000	11,200	11,233	11,538
200,000	8,700	8,675	9,479
200,000	9,767	8,675	9,479
200,000	8,000	8,675	9,479
200,000	8,233	8,675	9,479
400,000	5,767	7,350	7,374
400,000	9,367	7,350	7,374
400,000	7,867	7,350	7,374
400,000	6,400	7,350	7,374
800,000	4,400	5,958	5,402
800,000	6,600	5,958	5,402
800,000	5,600	5,958	5,402
800,000	7,233	5,958	5,402

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 57: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 7 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [µg/L]	11,938	33,352	238,091
lower 95%-cl	5,772	16,472	97,201
upper 95%-cl	24,689	68,235	566,784

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 10: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on yield TSL of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 7 d

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Yield TSL at 14 d

Yield TSL [cm] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 14 d.

Tab. 58: %Reduction of yield TSL caused by the test item after 14 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	37,13	3,139	6	
25,000	31,89	0,478	4	14,1
50,000	31,76	3,438	4	14,5
100,000	25,87	2,235	4	30,3
200,000	19,79	1,554	4	46,7
400,000	14,22	2,749	4	61,7
800,000	9,21	1,486	4	75,2

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration).

A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

The optimization converged thus fitting was successful (Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)).

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 59: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b0 - b2: parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t: t-statistic (Ho: b0|b1|b2 = 0); p(t): probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance (b1 = log EC10)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b0	36,900	0,944	34,964	38,837	39,099	<0.001
b1	1,427	0,107	1,208	1,646	13,375	<0.001
b2	0,751	0,068	0,611	0,890	11,020	<0.001

Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R²: 0,947; adjusted R²: 0,943. Residual standard error: 2,40609. Akaike Criterion (AIC): 89,119. ShapiroWilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: p = 0,513..

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 60: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p(F): probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	2808,88	2	1404,44	242,594	<0.001
Residuals	156,31	27	5,79		
- Lack of Fit	19,38	4	4,84	0,814	0,529
- Pure Error	136,93	23	5,95		
Total	2966,59	29			

Since p(F|Regression) <= 0.05, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model.. Since p(F|Lack of Fit) > 0.05, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 61: Observed values in yield TSL after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	37,667	37,133	36,900
0,001	37,100	37,133	36,900
0,001	39,467	37,133	36,900
0,001	36,400	37,133	36,900
0,001	40,600	37,133	36,900
0,001	31,567	37,133	36,900
25,000	32,033	31,892	33,455
25,000	32,500	31,892	33,455
25,000	31,600	31,892	33,455
25,000	31,433	31,892	33,455
50,000	29,067	31,758	30,296
50,000	35,633	31,758	30,296
50,000	28,667	31,758	30,296
50,000	33,667	31,758	30,296
100,000	27,233	25,867	25,752
100,000	27,033	25,867	25,752
100,000	26,667	25,867	25,752
100,000	22,533	25,867	25,752
200,000	20,367	19,792	20,173
200,000	19,233	19,792	20,173
200,000	21,600	19,792	20,173

200,000	17,967	19,792	20,173
400,000	12,400	14,217	14,329
400,000	18,300	14,217	14,329
400,000	13,333	14,217	14,329
400,000	12,833	14,217	14,329
800,000	8,733	9,208	9,105
800,000	8,767	9,208	9,105
800,000	11,367	9,208	9,105
800,000	7,967	9,208	9,105

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 62: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with yield TSL at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [µg/L]	26,732	57,185	244,948
lower 95%-cl	16,148	35,146	134,410
upper 95%-cl	44,253	93,206	440,533

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 11: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on yield TSL of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Overview over the ECs of the Test Item on Yield TSL

Effects on Yield TSL

Tab. 63: Yield TSL (YTL) and its inhibition relative to control (%I) as computed from the raw data for test intervals selected.; *nl with yield TSL: nonlinear regression using the 3-param. normal CDF.

Treatment [µg/L]	0-7 d		0-14 d	
	YTL	%I	YTL	%I

NK	17,82	0,0	37,13	0,0
25,000	14,88	16,5	31,89	14,1
50,000	14,17	20,4	31,76	14,5
100,000	11,23	37,0	25,87	30,3
200,000	8,67	51,3	19,79	46,7
400,000	7,35	58,7	14,22	61,7
800,000	5,96	66,6	9,21	75,2

EC10	11,938	*nl	26,732	*nl
lower95%-cl	5,772		16,148	
upper95%-cl	24,689		44,253	
EC20	33,352	*nl	57,185	*nl
lower95%-cl	16,472		35,146	
upper95%-cl	68,235		93,206	
EC50	238,091	*nl	244,948	*nl
lower95%-cl	97,201		134,410	
upper95%-cl	566,784		440,533	

Threshold concentrations (NOEC) for Yield TSL at 7 d

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 64: Statistical characteristics with yield TSL at 7 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	s%	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	17,82	17,47	16,53	20,53	6	1,439	8,1	0,588	3,3	16,31	19,33
25,000	14,88	15,08	14,00	15,37	4	0,622	4,2	0,311	2,1	13,89	15,87
50,000	14,17	14,23	11,70	16,53	4	2,041	14,4	1,020	7,2	10,93	17,42
100,000	11,23	11,32	10,27	12,03	4	0,734	6,5	0,367	3,3	10,07	12,40
200,000	8,67	8,47	8,00	9,77	4	0,784	9,0	0,392	4,5	7,43	9,92
400,000	7,35	7,13	5,77	9,37	4	1,607	21,9	0,803	10,9	4,79	9,91
800,000	5,96	6,10	4,40	7,23	4	1,237	20,8	0,619	10,4	3,99	7,93

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 65: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with yield TSL at 7 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(Ho) is accepted.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	n
NK	17,82	1,439	6
25,000	14,88	0,622	4
50,000	14,17	2,041	4
100,000	11,23	0,734	4
200,000	8,67	0,784	4
400,000	7,35	1,607	4
800,000	5,96	1,237	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 30; Shapiro-Wilk's W = 0,979; p(W) = 0,810; p(W) is greater than the selected

significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 66: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with yield TSL at 7 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	4,1084	6	0,6847	1,367	0,270
Residuals	11,5223	23	0,5010		
Total	15,631	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 67: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with yield TSL at 7 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	56,1417	3,2891	23	17,069	<0.001
Quadratic	-5,3917	5,7221	23	-0,942	0,178

The linear trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$) The quadratic trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 68: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with yield TSL at 7 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates $n(i)$; k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	17,82	1,3156						
25,000	14,88	1,3156	23	14,88	-8,2	-3,45	-1,71	+
50,000	14,17	1,3156	23	14,18	-8,5	-4,29	-1,78	+
100,000	11,23	1,3156	23	11,23	-8,6	-7,75	-1,81	+
200,000	8,67	1,3156	23	8,67	-8,7	-10,76	-1,82	+
400,000	7,35	1,3156	23	7,35	-8,7	-12,32	-1,83	+
800,000	5,96	1,3156	23	5,96	-8,7	-13,96	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

The NOEC is lower than 25,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 69: Statistical characteristics with yield TSL at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	s%	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	37,13	37,38	31,57	40,60	6	3,139	8,5	1,282	3,5	33,84	40,43
25,000	31,89	31,82	31,43	32,50	4	0,478	1,5	0,239	0,7	31,13	32,65
50,000	31,76	31,37	28,67	35,63	4	3,438	10,8	1,719	5,4	26,29	37,23
100,000	25,87	26,85	22,53	27,23	4	2,235	8,6	1,117	4,3	22,31	29,42
200,000	19,79	19,80	17,97	21,60	4	1,554	7,9	0,777	3,9	17,32	22,26
400,000	14,22	13,08	12,40	18,30	4	2,749	19,3	1,374	9,7	9,84	18,59
800,000	9,21	8,75	7,97	11,37	4	1,486	16,1	0,743	8,1	6,84	11,57

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 70: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with yield TSL at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(H_0) is accepted.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	n
NK	37,13	3,139	6
25,000	31,89	0,478	4
50,000	31,76	3,438	4
100,000	25,87	2,235	4
200,000	19,79	1,554	4
400,000	14,22	2,749	4
800,000	9,21	1,486	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 30; Shapiro-Wilk's $W = 0,982$; $p(W) = 0,880$; $p(W)$ is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 71: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with yield TSL at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	16,7028	6	2,7838	1,682	0,170
Residuals	38,0575	23	1,6547		
Total	54,760	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled. A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 72: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with yield TSL at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	131,0917	6,1000	23	21,491	<0.001
Quadratic	26,4083	10,6123	23	2,488	0,010

The linear trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$) The quadratic trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 73: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with yield TSL at 14 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates $n(i)$; k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	37,13	2,4400						
25,000	31,89	2,4400	23	31,89	-7,3	-3,33	-1,71	+
50,000	31,76	2,4400	23	31,76	-7,6	-3,41	-1,78	+
100,000	25,87	2,4400	23	25,87	-7,7	-7,15	-1,81	+
200,000	19,79	2,4400	23	19,79	-7,7	-11,01	-1,82	+
400,000	14,22	2,4400	23	14,22	-7,7	-14,55	-1,83	+
800,000	9,21	2,4400	23	9,21	-7,7	-17,73	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

The NOEC is lower than 25,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Overview over the Effect-Thresholds of the Test Item on Yield TSL

Overview over the LOEC and NOEC Determination

Tab. 74: Overview over the LOEC and NOEC Determination with yield TSL: Arithmetic means and significance marks as computed for yield TSL for all inspection intervals (top); bottom part: obtained LOEC and NOEC with indication of statistical test used; *wl: Williams multiple sequential t-test procedure, significance level was 0,050, one-sided smaller.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	0-7 d	0-14 d
25,000	14,88+	31,89+
50,000	14,17+	31,76+
100,000	11,23+	25,87+
200,000	8,67+	19,79+
400,000	7,35+	14,22+
800,000	5,96+	9,21+

Tab. 74 (continued): Overview over the LOEC and NOEC Determination with yield TSL: Arithmetic means and significance marks as computed for yield TSL for all inspection intervals (top); bottom part: obtained LOEC and NOEC with indication of statistical test used; *wl: Williams multiple sequential t-test procedure, significance level was 0,050, one-sided smaller.

LOEC <=25,000 *wl <=25,000 *wl

NOEC <25,000 *wl <25,000 *wl

+: Significant difference to control (p <=0,050)

Growth Rate TSL (Data)

Growth Rate TSL [1/d] of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as Dependent on Concentration and Time

Tab. 75: Growthrate TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time; Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation (calculated from RawData Tot Shoot Length)

Treatm. [µg/L]	NK	25,000	50,000	100,000	200,000	400,000	800,000
0 d	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
	0,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,000	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
Std.Dev.:	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:							
7 d	0,183	0,158	0,151	0,134	0,095	0,081	0,061
	0,184	0,161	0,148	0,134	0,110	0,119	0,085
	0,175	0,165	0,142	0,121	0,115	0,115	0,080
	0,191	0,153	0,145	0,135	0,111	0,082	0,086
	0,181	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,150	-	-	-	-	-	-

Tab. 75 (continued): Growth rate TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as dependent on concentration of the test item and time;
 Mean: arithmetic mean; Std.Dev.: standard deviation; n: number of replicates; CV: coefficient of variation
 (calculated from RawData Tot Shoot Length)

Mean:	0,177	0,159	0,146	0,131	0,108	0,099	0,078
Std.Dev.:	0,0144	0,0052	0,0037	0,0068	0,0088	0,0204	0,0114
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	8,1	3,3	2,5	5,2	8,1	20,6	14,7
14 d	0,133	0,118	0,115	0,108	0,084	0,070	0,052
	0,134	0,126	0,120	0,110	0,085	0,090	0,052
	0,136	0,123	0,117	0,107	0,105	0,080	0,066
	0,128	0,114	0,109	0,102	0,091	0,067	0,046
	0,139	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0,107	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean:	0,129	0,120	0,115	0,107	0,091	0,077	0,054
Std.Dev.:	0,0116	0,0054	0,0047	0,0035	0,0098	0,0107	0,0084
n:	6	4	4	4	4	4	4
CV:	8,9	4,5	4,1	3,3	10,8	14,0	15,6

Fig. 12: Growth rate TSL of *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed under presence of the test item after 14 d.

Effective Concentrations (EC_x) for Growth Rate TSL at 7 d

Growth Rate TSL [1/d] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 7 d.

Tab. 76: %Reduction of growth rate TSL caused by the test item after 7 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	0,177	0,0144	6	

25,000	0,159	0,0052	4	10,3
50,000	0,146	0,0037	4	17,5
100,000	0,131	0,0068	4	26,2
200,000	0,108	0,0088	4	39,1
400,000	0,099	0,0204	4	44,2
800,000	0,078	0,0114	4	56,1

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 77: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	0,178	0,005	0,169	0,187	39,441	<0.001
b_1	1,273	0,153	0,959	1,587	8,325	<0.001
b_2	1,121	0,120	0,874	1,368	9,313	<0.001

Stop Reason = Iterations > Max. Iterations (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,915; adjusted R^2 : 0,909. Residual standard error: 0,01123. Akaike Criterion (AIC): -232,926. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,268$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 78: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; $p(F)$: probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	0,034	2	0,017	136,681	<0.001
Residuals	0,003	27	0,000		
- Lack of Fit	0,000	4	0,000	0,437	0,781
- Pure Error	0,003	23	0,000		
Total	0,038	29			

Since $p(F|\text{Regression}) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model. Since $p(F|\text{Lack of Fit}) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit.

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 79: Observed values in growth rate TSL after 7 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	0,183	0,1773	0,1780
0,001	0,184	0,1773	0,1780
0,001	0,175	0,1773	0,1780
0,001	0,191	0,1773	0,1780
0,001	0,181	0,1773	0,1780
0,001	0,150	0,1773	0,1780
25,000	0,158	0,1591	0,1565
25,000	0,161	0,1591	0,1565
25,000	0,165	0,1591	0,1565
25,000	0,153	0,1591	0,1565
50,000	0,151	0,1464	0,1453

50,000	0,148	0,1464	0,1453
50,000	0,142	0,1464	0,1453
50,000	0,145	0,1464	0,1453
100,000	0,134	0,1309	0,1311
100,000	0,134	0,1309	0,1311
100,000	0,121	0,1309	0,1311
100,000	0,135	0,1309	0,1311
200,000	0,095	0,1080	0,1144
200,000	0,110	0,1080	0,1144
200,000	0,115	0,1080	0,1144
200,000	0,111	0,1080	0,1144
400,000	0,081	0,0990	0,0958
400,000	0,119	0,0990	0,0958
400,000	0,115	0,0990	0,0958
400,000	0,082	0,0990	0,0958
800,000	0,061	0,0779	0,0768
800,000	0,085	0,0779	0,0768
800,000	0,080	0,0779	0,0768
800,000	0,086	0,0779	0,0768

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 80: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [µg/L]	18,750	58,388	512,961
lower95%-cl	9,104	28,397	193,711
upper95%-cl	38,617	120,620	1275,869

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 13: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on growth rate TSL of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 7 d

Effective Concentrations (ECx) for Growth Rate TSL at 14 d

Growth Rate TSL [1/d] in *Myriophyllum spicatum* after 14 d.

Tab. 81: %Reduction of growth rate TSL caused by the test item after 14 d.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Mean	Std. Dev.	n	%Reduction
NK	0,129	0,0116	6	
25,000	0,120	0,0054	4	7,1
50,000	0,115	0,0047	4	11,0
100,000	0,107	0,0035	4	17,7
200,000	0,091	0,0098	4	29,6
400,000	0,077	0,0107	4	40,8
800,000	0,054	0,0084	4	58,3

The 3-param. normal CDF $F(x) = b_0 * [\text{NormalCDF}(b_1 - \log_{10}(x)/b_2 + z_{\text{Opt}})]$ was fitted to the data (CDF: cumulative distribution function; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; z_{Opt} : adjustment to have the EC10 as parameter b_1 ; x : concentration). A non-linear regression without weighting was performed.

The optimization converged thus fitting was successful (Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)).

Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 82: Estimated parameters of the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Results of the non-linear regression analysis; b_0 - b_2 : parameters; Std. Err.: standard error; 95%LCL|UCL: 95%-lower|upper confidence limits; t : t-statistic ($H_0: b_0|b_1|b_2 = 0$); $p(t)$: probability that the deviation from zero is due to chance ($b_1 = \log \text{EC}_{10}$)

Parameter	Value	Std. Err.	95%LCL	95%UCL	t	p(t)
b_0	0,129	0,003	0,122	0,135	41,761	<0.001
b_1	1,700	0,125	1,443	1,957	13,592	<0.001
b_2	0,831	0,096	0,634	1,028	8,648	<0.001

Stop Reason = Converged (Optimization method: Levenberg-Marquardt)

R^2 : 0,908; adjusted R^2 : 0,901. Residual standard error: 0,00810. Akaike Criterion (AIC): -252,547. Shapiro-Wilk's test on normal distribution of residuals: $p = 0,808$.

Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 83: Analysis of Variance and Test for Lack of Fit for the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Source:

source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p(F): probability that the variance explained by the regression is due to chance; Pure error: residual SS|MSS of an one-way ANOVA with the original data (CDF: cumulative distribution function)

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Regression	0,019	2	0,009	142,671	<0.001
Residuals	0,002	27	0,000		
- Lack of Fit	0,000	4	0,000	0,205	0,933
- Pure Error	0,002	23	0,000		
Total	0,021	29			

Since $p(F|Regression) \leq 0.05$, a significant amount of variance is explained by the regression model.. Since $p(F|Lack of Fit) > 0.05$, there is no significant lack of fit..

Observed and Predicted Results of the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 84: Observed values in growth rate TSL after 14 d as caused by the test item and predicted values as calculated from the function.

Treatm.[µg/L]	Observed	Mean Obs.	Predicted
0,001	0,133	0,1295	0,1286
0,001	0,134	0,1295	0,1286
0,001	0,136	0,1295	0,1286
0,001	0,128	0,1295	0,1286
0,001	0,139	0,1295	0,1286
0,001	0,107	0,1295	0,1286
25,000	0,118	0,1203	0,1222
25,000	0,126	0,1203	0,1222
25,000	0,123	0,1203	0,1222
25,000	0,114	0,1203	0,1222
50,000	0,115	0,1152	0,1158
50,000	0,120	0,1152	0,1158
50,000	0,117	0,1152	0,1158
50,000	0,109	0,1152	0,1158
100,000	0,108	0,1066	0,1056
100,000	0,110	0,1066	0,1056
100,000	0,107	0,1066	0,1056
100,000	0,102	0,1066	0,1056
200,000	0,084	0,0911	0,0915
200,000	0,085	0,0911	0,0915
200,000	0,105	0,0911	0,0915
200,000	0,091	0,0911	0,0915
400,000	0,070	0,0767	0,0743
400,000	0,090	0,0767	0,0743
400,000	0,080	0,0767	0,0743
400,000	0,067	0,0767	0,0743
800,000	0,052	0,0540	0,0558
800,000	0,052	0,0540	0,0558
800,000	0,066	0,0540	0,0558
800,000	0,046	0,0540	0,0558

Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF

Tab. 85: Point estimates from the 3-param. normal CDF with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Selected effective concentrations (ECx) of the test item; cl: confidence limit

Toxicity Metric	EC10	EC20	EC50
Value [µg/L]	50,112	116,306	582,289
lower 95%-cl	27,753	64,527	267,173
upper 95%-cl	90,484	210,000	1219,528

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons

The confidence limits of the EC10 used as a parameter were computed by means of the standard error of parameter b1; confidence limits for the remaining ECx were estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation using the parameter errors obtained from the inverse Hessian matrix (1000 runs)..

Fig. 14: Concentration-effect curve showing the influence of the test item on growth rate TSL of the introduced *Myriophyllum spicatum* as observed after 14 d

Overview over the ECs of the Test Item on Growth Rate TSL

Effects on Growth Rate TSL

Tab. 86: Growthrate TSL (GTL) and its inhibition relative to control (%) as computed from the raw data for test intervals selected.; *nl with growth rate TSL: nonlinear regression using the 3-param. normal CDF.

Treatment	0-7 d		0-14 d	
	[µg/L]	GTL	%I	GTL
NK	0,177	0,0	0,129	0,0
25,000	0,159	10,3	0,120	7,1
50,000	0,146	17,5	0,115	11,0
100,000	0,131	26,2	0,107	17,7
200,000	0,108	39,1	0,091	29,6
400,000	0,099	44,2	0,077	40,8
800,000	0,078	56,1	0,054	58,3
EC10	18,750	*nl	50,112	*nl

lower 95%-cl	9,104	27,753	
upper 95%-cl	38,617	90,484	
EC20	58,388	*nl 116,306	*nl
lower 95%-cl	28,397	64,527	
upper 95%-cl	120,620	210,000	
EC50	512,961	*nl 582,289	*nl
lower 95%-cl	193,711	267,173	
upper 95%-cl	1275,869	1219,528	

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 87: Statistical characteristics with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	0,177	0,182	0,150	0,191	6	0,0144	8,1	0,0059	3,3	0,162	0,192
25,000	0,159	0,160	0,153	0,165	4	0,0052	3,3	0,0026	1,6	0,151	0,167
50,000	0,146	0,146	0,142	0,151	4	0,0037	2,5	0,0018	1,3	0,141	0,152
100,000	0,131	0,134	0,121	0,135	4	0,0068	5,2	0,0034	2,6	0,120	0,142
200,000	0,108	0,111	0,095	0,115	4	0,0088	8,1	0,0044	4,1	0,094	0,122
400,000	0,099	0,098	0,081	0,119	4	0,0204	20,6	0,0102	10,3	0,067	0,131
800,000	0,078	0,082	0,061	0,086	4	0,0114	14,7	0,0057	7,4	0,060	0,096

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 88: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(H_0) is accepted.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	n
NK	0,177	0,0144	6
25,000	0,159	0,0052	4
50,000	0,146	0,0037	4
100,000	0,131	0,0068	4
200,000	0,108	0,0088	4
400,000	0,099	0,0204	4
800,000	0,078	0,0114	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 28; Shapiro-Wilk's $W = 0,948$; $p(W) = 0,174$; $p(W)$ is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 89: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	0,00061	6	0,00010	3,403	0,015
Residuals	0,00069	23	0,00003		
Total	0,0013	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneitycheck was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneityrequirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trendanalysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 90: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (H_0 : Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	0,45705	0,02932	23	15,589	<0.001
Quadratic	0,01066	0,05101	23	0,209	0,418

The linear trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$) The quadratic trend is not significant ($p > 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 91: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with growth rate TSL at 7 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; $df = N - k$; N: sum of treatment replicates $n(i)$; k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	0,177	0,01173						
25,000	0,159	0,01173	23	0,159	-7,3	-2,41	-1,71	+
50,000	0,146	0,01173	23	0,146	-7,6	-4,09	-1,78	+
100,000	0,131	0,01173	23	0,131	-7,7	-6,14	-1,81	+
200,000	0,108	0,01173	23	0,108	-7,8	-9,16	-1,82	+
400,000	0,099	0,01173	23	0,099	-7,8	-10,35	-1,83	+
800,000	0,078	0,01173	23	0,078	-7,8	-13,14	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

The NOEC is lower than 25,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Statistical Characteristics of the Samples

Tab. 92: Statistical characteristics with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean (X); Med: median; Min: minimum value, Max: maximum value; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; s%: coefficient of variation; s(X): standard error; %s(X): %standard error; 95%l, 95%u: lower, upper 95%-confidence limits.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	Med	Min	Max	n	s	%s	s(X)	%s(X)	95%l	95%u
NK	0,129	0,134	0,107	0,139	6	0,0116	8,9	0,0047	3,7	0,117	0,142
25,000	0,120	0,121	0,114	0,126	4	0,0054	4,5	0,0027	2,3	0,112	0,129
50,000	0,115	0,116	0,109	0,120	4	0,0047	4,1	0,0024	2,1	0,108	0,123
100,000	0,107	0,107	0,102	0,110	4	0,0035	3,3	0,0017	1,6	0,101	0,112
200,000	0,091	0,088	0,084	0,105	4	0,0098	10,8	0,0049	5,4	0,075	0,107
400,000	0,077	0,075	0,067	0,090	4	0,0107	14,0	0,0054	7,0	0,060	0,094
800,000	0,054	0,052	0,046	0,066	4	0,0084	15,6	0,0042	7,8	0,041	0,067

Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution

Tab. 93: Shapiro-Wilk's Test on Normal Distribution with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; p(ShapiroWilk's W): probability of the W statistic (i.e. that the observed deviations from the normal distributions are due to chance). In case p(ShapiroWilk's W) is greater than the chosen significance level, the normality hypothesis(Ho) is accepted.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	n
NK	0,129	0,0116	6
25,000	0,120	0,0054	4
50,000	0,115	0,0047	4
100,000	0,107	0,0035	4
200,000	0,091	0,0098	4
400,000	0,077	0,0107	4
800,000	0,054	0,0084	4

Results:

Number of residuals = 26; Shapiro-Wilk's $W = 0,962$; $p(W) = 0,428$; $p(W)$ is greater than the selected significance level of 0,010; thus treatment data do not significantly deviate from normal distribution.

Normality check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals)

Tab. 94: Levene's Test on Variance Homogeneity (with Residuals) with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Source: source of variance; SS: sum of squares; df: degrees of freedom; MSS: mean sum of squares; F: test statistic; p: probability that the variance explained by the treatment is due to chance

Source	SS	df	MSS	F	p(F)
Treatment	0,00015	6	0,00002	1,038	0,427
Residuals	0,00054	23	0,00002		
Total	0,0007	29			

The Levene test indicates variance homogeneity ($p > 0,010$).

Variance homogeneity check was passed ($p > 0,01$).

Normal-distribution and variance-homogeneity requirements are fulfilled.
A parametric multiple test is advisable.

To justify the use of Williams test at first a trend analysis by contrasts is performed.

Trend analysis by Contrasts (Monotonicity of Concentration/Response)

Tab. 95: Trend analysis by contrasts (monotonicity of concentration/response) with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Psi: sum of means weighted by contrasts; s(psi): standard error of psi; df: degrees of freedom; t: t-statistic; p(t): probability that the trend is due to chance (Ho: Slope = 0). Hypothesis of monotonicity is accepted if at least the linear contrast is significant.

Trend	Psi	s(psi)	df	t	p(t)
Linear	0,33781	0,02155	23	15,678	<0.001
Quadratic	0,12822	0,03749	23	3,420	0,001

The linear trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$) The quadratic trend is significant ($p \leq 0,05$)

The analysis of contrasts revealed a linear trend, thus the selected Williams test was performed.

Williams Multiple Sequential t-test Procedure

Tab. 96: Comparison of treatments with "NK" by the t test procedure after Williams with growth rate TSL at 14 d: Significance was Alpha = 0,050, one-sided smaller; Mean: arithmetic mean; n: sample size; s: standard deviation; LhM: max. likelihood mean; MDD: minimum detectable difference to NK (in percent of NK); t: sample t; t*: critical t for Ho: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \dots = \mu_k$; the differences are significant in case $|t| > |t^*|$ (The residual variance of an ANOVA was applied; df = N - k; N: sum of treatment replicates n(i); k: number of treatments). Note that the step-down test terminates after the first non-significant treatment is encountered

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	Mean	s	df	LhM	%MDD	t	t*	Sign.
NK	0,129	0,00862						
25,000	0,120	0,00862	23	0,120	-7,4	-1,65	-1,71	-
50,000	0,115	0,00862	23	0,115	-7,7	-2,56	-1,78	+
100,000	0,107	0,00862	23	0,107	-7,8	-4,12	-1,81	+
200,000	0,091	0,00862	23	0,091	-7,8	-6,89	-1,82	+
400,000	0,077	0,00862	23	0,077	-7,8	-9,49	-1,83	+
800,000	0,054	0,00862	23	0,054	-7,9	-13,57	-1,83	+

+: significant; -: non-significant

A NOEC of 25,000 $\mu\text{g/L}$ is suggested by the program.

Overview over the Effect-Thresholds of the Test Item on Growth Rate TSL

Overview over the LOEC and NOEC Determination

Tab. 97: Overview over the LOEC and NOEC Determination with growth rate TSL: Arithmetic means and significance marks as computed for growth rate TSL for all inspection intervals (top); bottom part: obtained LOEC and NOEC with indication of statistical test used; *wl: Williams multiple sequential t-test procedure, significance level was 0,050, one-sided smaller.

Treatm. [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	0-7 d	0-14 d
25,000	0,159+	0,120 -
50,000	0,146+	0,115+
100,000	0,131+	0,107+
200,000	0,108+	0,091+
400,000	0,099+	0,077+
800,000	0,078+	0,054+
LOEC	$\leq 25,000$ *wl	50,000 *wl
NOEC	$< 25,000$ *wl	25,000 *wl

+: Significant difference to control ($p \leq 0,050$)

Summary of Results for all Endpoints

Tab. 98: Summary of Results for all Endpoints: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

Critical Conc.s [$\mu\text{g/L}$]	0 - 14 d	
Yield FW		
	EC10	699,040
95%-CL	lower	567,122
	upper	861,642

Tab. 98 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

95%-CL	EC20	1055,297
	lower	719,913
	upper	1522,806
95%-CL	EC50	n.d.
	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
Yield FW	LOEC	400,000
	NOEC	200,000
Growth Rate FW		
95%-CL	EC10	1222,897
	lower	822,424
	upper	1818,375
95%-CL	EC20	n.d.
	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
95%-CL	EC50	n.d.
	lower	n.d.
	upper	n.d.
Growth Rate FW	LOEC	400,000
	NOEC	200,000
Yield DW		
95%-CL	EC10	0,000
	lower	0,000
	upper	n.d.

Tab. 98 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

	EC20	0,000	
95%-CL	lower	0,000	
	upper	n.d.	
	EC50	n.d.	
95%-CL	lower	n.d.	
	upper	n.d.	
Yield DW	LOEC	n.d.	
	NOEC	n.d.	
Growth Rate DW			
	EC10	0,000	
95%-CL	lower	n.d.	
	upper	n.d.	
	EC20	0,000	
95%-CL	lower	n.d.	
	upper	n.d.	
	EC50	n.d.	
95%-CL	lower	n.d.	
	upper	n.d.	
Growth Rate DW	LOEC	n.d.	
	NOEC	n.d.	
		0-7 d	0-14 d
Yield TSL			
	EC10	11,938	26,732
95%-CL	lower	5,772	16,148
	upper	24,689	44,253

Tab. 98 (continued): Summary of Results for all Endpoints: Critical effect and threshold concentration as observed at end of experimental time; EC: Effective concentration for xx% reduction; 95%-CL: 95% Confidence limits; LOEC: Lowest observed effect concentration; NOEC: No observed effect concentration.

95%-CL	EC20	33,352	57,185
	lower	16,472	35,146
	upper	68,235	93,206
95%-CL	EC50	238,091	244,948
	lower	97,201	134,410
	upper	566,784	440,533
Yield TSL	LOEC	<=25,000	<=25,000
	NOEC	<25,000	<25,000
Growth Rate TSL			
95%-CL	EC10	18,750	50,112
	lower	9,104	27,753
	upper	38,617	90,484
95%-CL	EC20	58,388	116,306
	lower	28,397	64,527
	upper	120,620	210,000
95%-CL	EC50	512,961	582,289
	lower	193,711	267,173
	upper	1275,869	1219,528
Growth Rate TSL	LOEC	<=25,000	50,000
	NOEC	<25,000	25,000

n.d.: not determined due to mathematical reasons or inappropriate data

Settings Table

Tab. 99:

Area	Item	Default Settings	User Settings
Global	Type of Exposure	Concentration	Concentration
	Extrapolation of ECx	By program	By program
	Show non-significant ECx	YES	YES
	Statistical design		NOEC/ECx
Variables	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	2	2
	Statistical pre-testing		

	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Monotonicity	Contrast Analysis	Contrast Analysis
	Sig. Level	0,05	0,05
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Williams
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller
	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Regr.	Non-linear Regr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt(IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt
	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
changeable	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlosimulation Not
Growth Rate FW	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	3	3
	Statistical pre-testing		
	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Monotonicity	Contrast Analysis	Contrast Analysis
	Sig. Level	0,05	0,05
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Williams
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller
	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Regr.	Non-linear Regr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt(IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt

	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
changeable	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlo simulation Not
Dry Weight	State	Selected for analysis	Deselected from analysis
Yield DW	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	2	2
	Statistical pre-testing		
	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Dunnett
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller
	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Regr.	Non-linear Regr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt (IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt
	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
changeable	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlo simulation Not
Growth Rate DW	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	3	3
	Statistical pre-testing		
	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Dunnett
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller

	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Regr.	Non-linear Regr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt(IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt
	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
changeable	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlo simulation Not
Shoot Length	State	Selected for analysis	Deselected from analysis
Yield SL	State	Selected for analysis	Deselected from analysis
Growth Rate SL	State	Selected for analysis	Deselected from analysis
Section-by-section GRSL	State	Selected for analysis	Deselected from analysis
Yield TSL	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	2	2
	Statistical pre-testing		
	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Monotonicity	Contrast Analysis	Contrast Analysis
	Sig. Level	0,05	0,05
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Williams
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller
	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Regr.	Non-linear Regr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt(IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt
	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
changeable	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlo simulation Not
Growth Rate TSL	State	Selected for analysis	Selected for analysis
	Data transformation	none	none
	Decimals data	3	3
	Statistical pre-testing		
	Normal distribution	Shapiro-Wilk's	Shapiro-Wilk's
	Significance level	0,01	0,01

	Variance homogeneity	Levene	Levene
	Significance level	0,01	0,01
	Who selected pre-tests	Program	Program
	Additional tests	None	None
	Monotonicity	Contrast Analysis	Contrast Analysis
	Sig. Level	0,05	0,05
	Final testing (NOEC)		
	Test procedure	Williams	Williams
	Who selected final test	Program	Program
	Variance used	Residual from ANOVA	Residual from ANOVA
	Significance level	0,05	0,05
	Test direction	one-sided smaller	one-sided smaller
	ECx computation		
	Selected ECx values	EC10, EC20, EC50	EC10, EC20, EC50
	Selected method	Non-linear Repr.	Non-linear Repr.
(IRLS)	Optimization	Levenberg-Marquardt (IRLS)	Levenberg-Marquardt
	Dose/resp. function metric	3-param Normal	3-param Normal
	Weights	Not used	Not used
	Calculation of confid. limits		Monte-Carlo simulation Not
changeable			
	Section-by-section	GRTSL	
	Deselected from analysis	State	Selected for analysis